

Des pas sur l'invisible

for Clarinet or Saxophone

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Work created in the context of the Frederico de Freitas
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Cover painting: Sofia Gomes. Solaris I, 2016.

Notation

The score comprises three staves corresponding to three main polarizing sounds: D4; D5 and D6 (transposed sounds) the fundamental, 2nd harmonic and 4th harmonic respectively. The importance of the octave interval between these three sounds is thus established, on the one hand, as the limit of a space to be filled or traveled, and on the other hand as an intensive space: where different tensions, movements and temporalities are generated.

In the space thus defined the following main effects are attributed:

Continuously sustained note without vibrato (S.V.).

Momentary interruption of the actual presence of the note D4 (transposed sound).

Quarter tone below.

Quarter tone above.

Sung sound in glissando between the annotated notes. It is also transposed. If necessary, sing to the octave.

Glissando. Do not emphasize intermediate notes.

Measured vibratto.

Air sounds.

Duration: 4' cca.

A musical score for a single staff, likely a violin or flute, featuring a variety of dynamics and articulations. The score is divided into four measures, each with a dynamic marking and a crescendo or decrescendo hairpin. The first measure starts with a forte (*f*) dynamic and a decrescendo hairpin, followed by a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic and a crescendo hairpin. The second measure begins with a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic and a decrescendo hairpin, leading to a forte (*f*) dynamic and a crescendo hairpin. The third measure starts with a forte (*f*) dynamic and a decrescendo hairpin, transitioning to a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic and a crescendo hairpin. The fourth measure begins with a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic and a decrescendo hairpin, moving to a piano (*p*) dynamic and a crescendo hairpin. The score includes various articulations such as accents, slurs, and trills. A treble clef is positioned at the bottom center of the page.

12" 12" 12"

